

EXTRALINGUISTIC ISSUES IN CROSS-CULTURAL COMMUNICATION: BODY LANGUAGE, TABOO.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7902853>

Abstract: This thesis about Cross-cultural communication is a field of .Study that looks at how people from differing cultural backgrounds communicate, in same and different ways among themselves, and how they endeavor to communicate across cultures. The following article gives information about effective means of cross-cultural communication, non-verbal communication and taboo.

Key words: extralinguistic, taboo, non-verbal communication, body language.

Extralinguistic - a state outside the boundaries of linguistics; however, this is a free sample that can be found in any educational field. In the field of linguistics, extra-linguistic elements are considered because they provide information related to motivation, emotions, attitudes, personality, etc., which have been proven to help a student acquire certain languages. In this paper, the researcher has linked several auxiliary and non-linguistic elements in language learning that are necessary to show how other language learners perceive and are ready to learn languages other than their mother tongue. Every student or teacher should recognize that learning a second language requires more than just reading, writing, or speaking the language they want to learn, but also additional efforts to make learning a second language more meaningful. Teachers should seriously consider the presence of extralinguistics in language learning, because the elements in it help students to learn any language easily. Extralinguistic elements are crucial for educational success. Students, teachers, parents, schools and the Ministry of Education should be more concerned to ensure student success. Contribution/Uniqueness: This study is based on the researcher's own experience teaching English as a second language, including the privilege of teaching Japanese as a third language. This study is the first of its kind to help teachers and educators identify additional linguistic elements that influence students' second language learning. When it comes to cross-cultural communication, we can learn a number of differences. This includes body language and taboo.

Communication is not just the use of words to express a thought or idea. Being able to communicate goes beyond simple words to express yourself; there are also non-verbal means of communication. Non-verbal communication method is called body language. Body language is how people express themselves without saying anything. It can be a conscious act or state or an unconscious act or state. People are able to show their emotions through body movements. They use specific hand gestures, facial expressions, eye contact, and body positioning. For example: When someone blinks, you'll usually see their eyebrows raise slightly for less than $\frac{1}{5}$ of a second. What it means: An eyebrow is raised. is a great sign of interest. People use eyebrow light in three main ways:

A flick of the eyebrow can indicate professional interest, as in approving, agreeing to something, thanking someone, or asking for approval. Used as a non-verbal "yes" during conversation. An eyebrow lamp can also show interest in a romantic way. Or an eyebrow flash can indicate social interest because the 2 people know each other. It tells the other person

that you are happy to see them. When we use eyebrow light, we focus on our face. Teachers and speakers often do this by saying, "Listen to this!" Or "Look at me!" Interestingly, some cultures, such as the Japanese, consider this gesture inappropriate and avoid it. Facial expressions are an integral part of body language, so photographs of faces are the most common stimulus for learning to perceive emotions. Atkinson notes that responses to facial expressions of emotion are highly correlated. In support of this finding, Ekman (2009) explains that certain facial expressions have universal meaning. For example, when a person is happy, they usually smile and their faces generally give off more energy. At the same time, the absence of a smile is usually taken as a sign of sadness. Hands and Feet - The placement of the hands and feet can also indicate emotions. For example, crossed arms can indicate defensiveness or a desire to protect oneself (Foley & Gentile, 2010). Hands on hips can also be an expression of aggression or show that a person feels ready and in control. Crossed legs can also be an expression of a need for privacy and can indicate a feeling of being closed off.

A taboo is an action that is considered inappropriate and inappropriate to practice or even talk about within a cultural group. A synonym for taboo is prohibition. The word taboo comes from the Tongan word tabu or tapu, which roughly translates to "forbidden." Captain James Cook learned about taboos during his voyages across the Pacific in the 18th century and brought the term back to England.

Examples of cultural taboos

Not tipping at a restaurant (US) - Although tipping is not considered common in countries like New Zealand and Australia, it is considered rude in the United States.

Pointing to someone's chest (Global) - Many nations around the world adopt a common gesture. However, pointing directly at someone (especially their breasts) is considered rude and provocative.

Eating with your fingers - Eating with your fingers in a formal setting is considered very rude and low class. However, eating with your fingers is recommended for more working class or certain foods like pizza and wings.

Chewing gum in public - chewing gum can be considered low class. It can also be related to dirt, as chewing gum is often spat out on the streets.

Alcohol consumption (conservative Arab nations) - While alcohol is celebrated in much of Europe, some conservative Arab nations consider it a morally questionable activity. This probably stems directly from Islamic beliefs.

Unfortunately, cultural, religious and food taboos vary widely around the world. While some are almost universal (such as moral taboos such as cheating and stealing), others are very specific to countries or regional cultural groups.

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